

A Review of New Leadership Theories and Its Components

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Abstract

The Humanities thinkers discuss the concept of leadership from a variety of dimensions. A group considers leadership as a part of the management's duties; another group believes there is a broader concept for leadership compared to management, and they consider it as the ability to persuade others to diligently seek to achieve certain goals, or they see them as activities that influence people to endeavor enthusiastically in order to achieve the influential group's goals, and others define leadership as influencing people to achieve a common goal (Rezaiean, 2011). Despite many definitions given about the leadership, some common points among all the above could be yet emphasized in case of the leadership definition. These common points are as follows

(A) Leadership is a process (B) Leadership is mixed with change (C) Leadership occurs within a group (D) Leadership is purposeful (Afjeie, 2011).

This article has deeply dealt with this issue

Key words: leadership; management; style; model

1. Introduction

Leadership approaches and theories have been developed to introduce new ways of thinking that can help researchers, focusing on problematic areas, to decide for the situations that might be tried by leaders (Hoy & Miskel¹, 2013). In this section, we will first briefly review the traditional approaches and a succinct description of the approaches as well as new leadership theories that explain the characteristics of effective leadership. Studies and researches conducted in the field of leadership have led to the emergence of numerous approaches and theories. Tables 1 and 2 show a summary of the evolutionary process of leadership traditional and modern approaches and theories with their significant components.

Table 1 Traditional Leadership Approaches and Theories and Their Components

Approach/ Theory	Presenter	Year of presentation	Components and features
Trait Theory ²	Stagdbble and House ³	1904	It emphasizes on the leaders' characteristics and views, believing leadership to be intrinsic as well as the capabilities and features concerning leadership
Behavioral Theories ⁴	Researchers of Iowa ⁵ , Ohio ⁶ and Michigan Universities, McGregor ⁷	1973	Determining the leader's styles and ways to behave subordinates, emphasis on the leader's behavior, relation between leadership style with leader's power and subordinates' tendency to obey, leadership being an acquisition, training people to prepare them for leadership positions
Contingency Leadership ⁸	Fred E. Fiedler ⁹	1967	The performance of the leader is influenced by the extent of his separation and his influence, emphasis on the environment and the conditions of the group, emphasis on the structure and position of the group, emphasis on power from the leader's position.
Path- Goal Theory ¹⁰	Evanz ¹¹ , House and Mitchell ¹²	1970 1974	Emphasis on the adaptation of the leader's behaviors to the conditional circumstances (including the characteristics of the staff and the features of the work environment); The way the leader influences the subordinates' perceptions of the work and personal goals of the relation between these two categories of goals in line with the influences on the employees' satisfaction;

Approach/ Theory	Presenter	Year of presentation	Components and features
			Leader's acceptance by subordinates and motivation for work performance.
Charismatic leadership ¹³	Weber ¹⁴ House	1947 1977	Emphasis on the leader's symbolic behavior; inspirational and dream messages; non-verbal communication; tendency towards ideological values; intellectual distortion of followers by the leader; change in his followers due to changes in their goals, values, needs, beliefs and dreams.
Leader- Participation ¹⁵	Wroom & Yetoon ¹⁶	1973	Expresses the relationship between the behavior of the leader-subordinates and the change in the level of participation of individuals in decision making according to different situations and attention to the results of performance; the provision of laws in order to determine the specific strategy; observing the set of laws and regulations; attention to different environmental conditions.
Function Leadership	Hersey & Blanchard ¹⁷	1977	The degree of efficiency and effectiveness of each particular style of leadership depends on the existence of appropriate conditions; the choice of style consistent with the position at a given time.
Interactive Leadership	Burns ¹⁸	1978	Maintaining the status quo; Governing a relationship between the leader and the subordinate; Determining the requirements of the work of subordinates to achieve their goals and those of organization; Search for deviations from the laws and regulations; Adopt corrective action; emphasize tactical outcomes; reward subordinates according to their achievements; conditional rewards.

Table 2 Modern Leadership Approaches and Theories and Their Components

Approach/ Theory	Presenter	Year of presentation	Components and features
Full Range Leadership Model (FRL) ²⁰	Boss & Avolio ²¹	1993	A pattern based on a hierarchical model; placing leadership functions on a range of passive, ineffective and active activities; including three types of interactive, transformational and passive / avoiding leadership styles, including three behavioral consequences: much effort, effective leadership and satisfaction; a better explanation of leadership processes; leader's noticing the mistakes and distortions; the most effective leadership is that it regularly engages in transformational leadership behaviors (ideal influence, individual considerations, inspirational motivation, mental stimulation) and utilizes the conditional rewards of interactive leadership.
Strategy Leadership ²²	Tylor ²³	1960	The effectiveness of the leader on the desirable organizational success and organizational culture; high-resolution decision-making; oriented, long-term and fundamental decisions; the system's structure through the development of organizational learning, the influence of

Approach/ Theory	Presenter	Year of presentation	Components and features
			constructive loops and the interactive structure of the organization; providing a more influential context through confidence building and development of social capital within and outside the system and potential motivating development; guidance through policy-making and consensus over a complex, ambiguous, unreliable, and volatile global environment; the optimal allocation of resources; taking into account all desires; Personality differences, various programs, stakeholders of organization and cultures.
Servant Leadership ²⁴		1997	Equality of leader with subordinates in line with directing them; the equality of all members of the organization in the rights, information and vision of the organization; the role of the leader as a facilitator in the formation of the group and organization.
Transformational Leadership	Burns & Boss ²⁵	1978	Emphasizing the moral characteristics and transcendental ideals such as freedom, justice, equality, peace and humanity; motivating subordinates to further work towards achieving the goals of the organization; raising the level of awareness of the importance and value of specific results in subordinates ; forcing subordinates to go beyond individual interests for the sake of team, organization and system; Improving the needs levels of subordinates to higher-level needs; Emphasizing the ideal influence; Inspiring motivation; Rational stimulation; Individual considerations.
Authentic Leadership ²⁹	Leadership Institution	2004	Focus on self-regulation and self-awareness of the leader and followers; the positive role of organizational moderator and emphasis on function.
Spiritual Leadership ³⁰	Brown & Trevino ³¹	2006	Emphasizing the values, beliefs and behaviors of individuals and giving them incentives; spiritual commitment and survival; joint decision-making between the leader and subordinates; honesty, truthfulness and mutual trust between the leader and the followers, and attention to the work results.

Source: Using (Vanderwerf, 2007; Washington and Field, 2006; Humphreys & Einstein, 2003; Leban and Zulauf, 2004; Mandel & Pherwani; 2003; Turkzade; 2009; Sohrabpour, 2006).

2. New Leadership Approaches and Theories

2.1 Transformational Leadership³²

These days, organizations need leaders who can create sufficient commitment, passion and enthusiasm in subordinates to use their ultimate talents and make their best efforts to achieve organizational objectives with the help of their own characteristics, exceptional attraction features, high influence power as well as wide vision. Such leaders are now called transformational leaders (“Javdani”, 2011). Transformational Leadership Style is known as a more effective leadership style than that of Interactive. The Transformational Leadership Style is considered as one of the most influential and appropriate leadership styles in a dynamic environment. The Transformational Leadership that scientists and experts are increasingly focusing on is one of the new leadership styles that was first introduced by “James Burns”³³ in 1978. Burns (1978) defines the Transformational Leader as “someone who searches for the potential motives of the subordinates, seeks to meet higher-ranking needs, and induces a subordinate to establish a mutually reinforcing relationship and promotional methods that make a leaders out of him.” In 1985, based on Burns's theory, Bernard Bass³⁴ said that transformational leaders can provoke their followers to do more than what they are expected to. Burns further argued that this leadership

style occurs when one or more people interact with others in a way in which leaders and subordinates improve each other to higher levels of ethics and motivation. This leadership style argued that leaders and subordinates increase the sense of accomplishment of a superior goal and each other's motivation (Sanlam and O'Higgins, 2012). The Transformational Leadership has moved from the older perspectives of the leader-oriented theory to the newer perspectives of process-oriented theory. According to Burns (1978), Transformational Leadership show individuals' higher-level needs for success, self-confidence and self-esteem. This style encourages individuals to look beyond personal interests for the sake of achieving a common and desirable organizational interest and will promote leaders and subordinates to higher levels of motivation and ethics. This reflects the way how people ask for their needs, desires, interests and preferences. Tichy and Devanna³⁵ (1990) believe that Transformational Leader is interacting during a process. This interaction involves a range of consequences that involve recognizing the need for change, creating a new perspective, and institutionalizing the change. In Transformational Leadership, people are trustworthy and purposeful, and each one has a special partnership to create a desirable function (Nusair³⁶ and et al., 2012). In Table 2-3, the similarities and differences between transformational leadership and interactive leadership are explained.

Table 3 similarities and differences between Transformational Leadership and Interactive Leadership

	Transformational Leader	Interactive Leader
	Ideal Influence: Providing insight and sense of pragmatism, injection of pride and glory, gaining respect and trust.	Conditional Bonus (Appropriate): A rewards contract with efforts, promise rewards for good performance.
	Inspirational motivation: Transferring high level expectations, using symbols to focus on efforts, expressing important goals in simple ways.	Management on the basis of Exception (Active): Look for deviations from the rules and standards, adopt corrective action.
	Rational Stimulation: Promoting Intelligence, Rationality, and Precise Problem Solving.	Management on the basis of Exception (Passive): Interventions, provided that the standards are not met.
	Individual Considerations: Paying attention to individual differences, Dealing with employees individually, instructing and advice.	Unrestrained (free): assign and delegate responsibilities, avoid making decisions.
	It is already mixed with values, ethics, spirituality, and goals.	It is already mixed with power and success and politics.
	It is beyond daily affairs.	Drowned in daily affairs.
	Without imperiling human principles, it tends to pursue a long-term goal.	It tends to have short-term goals and a tendency to know why and why.
	It emphasizes success strategies.	Emphasizes tactical outcomes.
	It emphasizes the utilization of available resources.	In interactions, it emphasizes human relationships.
	It designs and reviews businesses to make them meaningful and challenging and seeks to understand human abilities.	Through making efforts to reach effective work, expectations follow the role.

Source: Duckett and Macfarlane (2003)

2. Strategic Leader

Michelle and Guilot³⁷ (2005), Hans, Hinterhuber and Stephan³⁸ (2002) argue that strategic leadership is a general and difficult concept, which seeks to make the desirable future by determining destinations, selecting the best solutions and properly applying the best equipment in a position proportional with the organization domestic conditions and the strategic environment requirements . In this effort, the Strategic Leader must be able to best fit the environmental

opportunities and the leadership's intentions as well as the resources of the organization (system), and develop and apply the strategy as a joint between the external changing world and the internal resources of the organization in a way that lead to the acquisition of competitive advantage³⁹ and the realization of strategic desirability of the organization (Turkzadeh, 2009); therefore, strategic leadership in practice is a special effort consisting of identifying strategic orientation, communication, adaptability and management of the interactive environment to influence the present and future situation of the organization and the environment. It seeks to make the desirable future through interaction with other conditions and factors by changing the organizational pattern, the desired situation or orientation. The strategic leader must try to change the current conceptual⁴⁰, structural⁴¹ and functional⁴² systems of the organization under his leadership as well as its interactive environment to profoundly respond to the circumstances and the present and future changes that are intended to be followed now and later. (Turkzadeh, 2009).

The mission of the strategic leadership is to provide and guarantee the military health and sustain the organization's meaningful survival. Organizational health can include the effectiveness, responsiveness to the environment, and maintaining the integrity of the organization at the same time. Accordingly, the core mission of strategic leadership is to ensure system integrity and correct work and maintain the active and dynamic balance of the organization in responding to the conditions and requirements of the strategic environment simultaneously (system health) and, consequently, the sustainability of the organization's meaningful survival. The three basic elements of strategic leadership that provide its basis are: absorptive capacity⁴³ (the ability of an individual or organization to learn, the capacity to recognize new knowledge and its integration, absorption and application for new goals and objectives with the aim of creating new and more harmony between the system and the environment); adaptive capacity⁴⁴ (the capacity or ability of the individual or organization to change; change of the organization; their own circumstances and behavior; and change of the environment); managerial wisdom⁴⁵ (the discerning and discernment⁴⁶ of the social position as well as kairos time⁴⁷) (Turkzadeh, 2009).

Servant Leadership

The Servant Leadership was first introduced in 1977 and based on Stewardship theory (Russell & Ston⁴⁸, 2002; Washington and Field⁴⁹, 2006; Gholipour and et al., 2009). Leadership can play an important and vital role in the future of organizations and communities leadership (Humphreys⁵⁰, 2005). Based on this approach, great leaders have been great servants, and this has been the key to their success (Horsman⁵¹, 2001). Therefore, the servant leadership is: the perception and function of the leader in such a way as to prefer the interests of others to his own desire and interest. Servant leaders are a model example for their followers and other individuals. They have very deep relationships with employees and help them to discover their potentials. The characteristics of the servant leaders are: effective listening, empathy, healing, awareness, persuasion, conceptualization, foresight and vision (providence), supervision (Stewardship and wardship), emphasis and focus on individuals, commitment to the growth and development of individuals, respect to the dignity of the people, formation by creating the group, building mutual trust and influence on followers, modeling, empowerment, competence and aptness (Omoh⁵², 2007).

2-4 Full Range Leadership

Based on the primary findings of Transformational Leadership and Interaction Leadership Studies, Bass and Avolio (1993) presented a Full Range Leadership Model in order to better explain the effective leadership processes. A Full Range Leadership Model is a hierarchy that represents the functions of leadership with a range of active-passive and effective- ineffective. The main assumption in this pattern is that a leader can use both transformational leadership and interactive leadership, especially its contingent reward. The most influential leaders are those who regularly use transformational leadership behaviors (ideal influence, inspirational motivation, rational stimulation, individual considerations), and conditional reward for interactive leadership. In this case, interactive leadership complements transformational leadership. The contingent reward of interactive leadership plays a leading role and creates trust, reassurance and consistency among followers. For this reason, these leaders provide their clear and recognizable expectations, which is a fundamental basis for transformational leadership in obtaining acceptable levels of performance (Avolio and Gardner, 2005). Transformational Leadership is added to the impacts of interactive leadership rewarding to increase followers' functions by highlighting high ethical standards and ethical behaviors of motivating the followers, inspiring ideas for creativity, and addressing needs and concerns. In short, the priority of behaviors increases in the Full Range Leadership Model from top to bottom; therefore, effective leadership depends on the extent to which leaders take advantages of each behavior (Avolio and Gardner, 2005).

2-5 Spiritual Leadership

Spiritual Leadership includes values, beliefs and behaviors that intrinsically motivate oneself and others. The basis of this approach is spiritual intelligence and its main element is love. Also, individuals with spiritual leadership succeed in membership, commitment, and culture that bring about a kind of spiritual survival. In other words, one can describe spiritual leadership as follows: Spiritual Leadership occurs when a person in the position of the leader represents spiritual values such as honesty, truthfulness, trustworthiness and admiration; also, he emphasizes the provision of service to others, an overall perspective on work, individual development, and joint decision making (Garcia-Morales⁵³ and et al., 2012). In sum, the importance and necessity of spirituality in the workplace is so much that can be accountable for organizations, humanity and society, activities and the environment.

2-6. Authentic Leadership

The Authentic Leadership theory was first introduced in 2004 by the Gallup Institute of the University of Nebraska-Lincoln⁵⁴. The main distinction of this theory with other recent theories on leadership is that the theory of Authentic Leadership is more general and focuses on the root structure that forms the positive leadership (Avolio and Gardner⁵⁵, 2005). The noble leadership theory focuses on self-regulation and self-awareness of the leader and followers, and trust and honesty. In most cases, this kind of leadership transmits itself in action, not words, in the form of principles, values, and morals (Avolio and Gardner, 2005; Fry Louis and et al.⁵⁶, 2008).

3 Review theories

Various studies have been conducted in relation to leadership under the title of personality traits (Dweck⁵⁷, 1999), the skills and capabilities of leaders (Groysberg and et al.⁵⁸, 2006), Leaders' Knowledge (Hogan & Kaiser⁵⁹, 2005). According to numerous studies, leadership has been defined based on a group effort to solve a problem (Van Vugt and et al.⁶⁰, 2008). In this approach, the influence of leadership style has been studied from the perspective of the leader's role and the extent to which the effort has been combined to achieve the performance.

Albert⁶¹ (2003) examines the theory of transformational leadership in the workplaces of Jamaica. Based on the results of this study, there was a correlation between the dimension of individual consideration and the outcome of satisfaction.

Nicolina⁶² (2003) examined the appropriateness of the transformational leadership style in educational institutions and environments. The results of this study showed that the transformational leadership style has a positive correlation with the effectiveness outcome.

Web⁶³ (2003) examined the degree of University heads' leadership behavior with followers' job satisfaction and the motivation to go beyond the expectations as well as effectiveness of leadership in colleges and universities. The findings of this study showed that the combination of transformational behaviors and better predictive relationships is one of the best predictors for job satisfaction and leadership effectiveness compared to transformational behaviors alone. Bommer and Baldwin⁶⁴ (2004) found that leaders whose homogeneous group leaders had more transformational leadership behavior tend to show more tendency to transformational leadership behavior.

Adizes⁶⁵ (2004) explores how to define and describe management styles in reality in a research entitled Management and Mismanagement Styles. He claims that any permutation⁶⁶ of the combination of these roles creates a kind of style. A good manager is the one who fulfills the function threshold needs⁶⁷ in all these roles, even if he is not the best in all roles. A managerial style can be a producer (Paei), an administrator (pAei), an entrepreneur (PaEi), or an integrator (paeI), etc. If that style is ineffective in one or more of its roles, it is a mismanagement style⁶⁸. If each role meets the minimum threshold needs, it is a management style. Finally, if the role of integrity (I) works well, in addition to at least one other role, and none of the roles is contradictory, it is a leadership style. However, in order to change from a good manager into a leader, meeting the threshold needs for each role is insufficient. For leadership, one must have at least two roles, one of which is role (I). And even afterwards, whether the combination of these two roles will create a responsible functional⁶⁹ leadership style will depend on this specific function of the manager or on what stage of his life cycle he will be. Adizes also states that in this work, the code (PAEI) can be used beyond the coding of behavior or style. (PAEI) roles are created in a predictable sequence of each organization's life cycle. Over time, some roles are more specific and other roles are less clear. This creates a pattern of problems that can be predicted and prevented. In other words, once you understand this template, you will have the means to identify what is normal and what is unusual at any stage of the life cycle. It's almost like keeping a crystal ball in your hands: in the light of the problems you have today, you can predict the next generation

of your problems. Whether the organization requires the (PaeI), (PaeI), or (paEI) leadership depends on is the life cycle stage the organization is having. As the organization grows and its age rises, the appropriate leadership style should also change, just like the parent's style depends on the age of the child.

Adizes also states that over the years of experiencing PAEI's style in more than 100 different organizations, communication has become easier, spirits are rising and productivity is increasing in those organizations. People's attitudes toward the positive side are changing, and co-operation and empathy are easily achieved. People really try to help each other (Adizes, 1998).

In general, when looking at the PAEI perspective, we will see a pyramidal organization with a multi-layered structure. In its bottom, almost all P could be found. Then there is an A layer and there is an E layer at its highest level. Layer I does not exist. In the hierarchic organizations, it is expected that everyone will act on the basis of the chain of command and will not break the official channels. If there is a responsibility to integrate, it often relates to the organizational development that is tied to the corners or the middle level of the organization (I).

In 2010, Jefferson⁷⁰ conducted a research entitled "Applied Performance Evaluation for Leadership". In this research, although the assessment of leadership performance in organizational success is more important than employees, more research is done on employee performance and how it is evaluated.

Huang⁷¹ and et al. (2010), did a research entitled "Does collaborative leadership promote task related performance through empowerment or trust?" (Surveys in managerial and non-managerial subcategories). The outcomes of this study are the results of a survey among 527 Forten employees. They found that there is a relationship between participatory leadership and functional performance as well as organizational citizenship behavior (OCB) through the empowerment of low-level managers. While there exists a collaborative leadership role on task performance for non-top managers including first-level supervisors and staff members and OCB has a mediator role through trust management.

Garcia Morales⁷² and et al. (2012) in their study examined the impact of transformational leadership on organizational performance through the dynamic capabilities of organizational learning and organizational innovation that was not explored in previous studies. Their study confirms these effects experimentally, based on a sample analysis of 168 Spanish companies. Their research results show that: (1) transformational leadership positively affects organizational performance through organizational learning and innovation; (2) organizational learning is positive both directly and indirectly through Organizational innovation affects organizational performance; (3) Organizational innovation positively affects organizational performance.

Ojokuku⁷³ and et al. (2012) in his research entitled "The Impact of Leadership Style on Organizational Performance: Case Study of Nigerian Banks" by using purposeful sampling technique to select a sample of 60 respondents and collecting data- By using the standard questionnaire and analyzing the data using inferential statistics and Pearson's correlation, they found that there was a positive and negative correlation between the dimensions of leadership style and organizational performance and that the dimensions of leadership style were jointly preceded by Organizational performance is responsible for 23% of the performance variance. Similarly, the results showed that, in order to achieve a competitive advantage, bank management should adopt a transformational and democratic leadership style.

In 2013, Carter⁷⁵ conducted a research entitled Strategic Leadership: Values, Styles and Organizational Performance. Generally speaking, leadership can be defined as the use of skills and expertise to guide and help people in terms of performance improvement. Leadership consists of receiving feedback from people, reinforcing them and turning them into constructive and practical suggestions for improvement. This requires that everyone can improve and improve, and can be helped to help them out.

Eiriz⁷⁶ and et al. (2013) investigated the phenomenon of innovation in the organizational life cycle in a research entitled Innovation Strategy and Innovation. They examined diverse life cycle models. The results of the studies show that the work of Greener and others on the growth of the company since the 1970s has helped expand the popularization⁷⁷ process models, both in practice and in theory. Another prominent work was done by Hanks, Watson, Jansen and Chandler⁷⁸ (1993), which reviewed the research literature on growth and compared the ten life cycle modeling models. While some models have very few steps (Smith, Michelle, and Summer⁷⁹, 1985, identified three steps), some models have more stages, most studies on the models show that some of them adapt with Adizes' life cycle and the quadruple roles (Adizes, 1989, identifies 10 steps).

Andonovic⁸⁰ and et al. (2014) presented an integrated model for distributing functional roles within work teams based on the Adizes model. The study of this mixed approach, which uses the combination of PAEI model and the role of the job analysis approach, suggests that this integrated model can be a predictable behavioral model, and from the approach the traditional experience can largely be ignored. In practice, this model can be regarded as more and more important than the acceptable level of interviewing job descriptions, as well as job appraisal conditions. Because in the new approach people are required to have skills and training based on the amount and role of the role and task involved in working teams. Other achievements of this research are to examine the results of the integrated model with the PAEI Adizes model.

Poor⁸¹ and et al. (2014) reviewed the researchers who focused on the various stages of the company's development for many years on issues related to financial management, sales and marketing. In contrast, Lavoie and Culbert⁸² (1978) and Adizes (1988) were among the first to draw attention to the fact that the solution used in human resource management as well as employee behavior patterns, along with developments in the life cycle The organization has undergone changes. The organizational cycle that Adizes has, properly portrayed the dominant role of the executives in its various stages.

In 2014, a study by Vermeeren⁸³ et al. On the impact of supervisory leadership style on the deployment of HR functions was reviewed. The analysis of data from a comprehensive international survey was conducted on 6,253 employees of the Dacs Company located in the Netherlands. They tested their assumptions using structural equations modeling. The results of the research indicate that the motivational leadership style dimension has a positive effect on the level of human resource performance.

Gao and Banerji⁸⁴ (2015) In China, to assess the growth and development of small and medium-sized enterprises, models have been used to formulate the leadership role of companies and middle-sized enterprises, which led to the selection and explanation of a suitable model Is. The results show that step-by-step models, such as the Five-Step Greiner⁸⁵ Framework (1972) and the Adizes Model for the Organizational Life Cycle (2004), are the most popular models used by researchers, policymakers, and administrators - Owners to describe the SME growth process and play an effective leadership role in organizations. In the meantime, the existence of a flat and hierarchical organization system, personal management style, flexibility within the framework of working teams, and also intuition-based strategies were selected as the main characteristics of the management of small and medium organizations. On the other hand, features such as financial constraints and human resources were selected as operational features of these organizations. Based on these characteristics, the competitive environment for small and medium enterprises is divided into three layers of industrial environments (first layer), national environments (second layer), and global environments (third layer) Were categorized. Accordingly, the classification of factors influencing the leadership of small and medium enterprises includes entrepreneurial characteristics, resource management and financial management, and innovation and technology management, business conduct, customer orientation and marketing, environments External. These are the characteristics of the leadership of small and medium sized organizations for the country with the fastest economic growth in the world. Given the above, the conceptual framework of leadership in the above organizations is described in Figures 2-6.

Figure1. Leader's Function Framework in Growth of SME Organizations

Larson⁸⁶ and et al. (2015) in a research entitled Industrial Engineering Leadership, examined the styles of project leaders on project performance. In this research, the main focus is on emerging and modern styles. The results and achievements have shown that over the last 50 years five schools have emerged in leadership literature, some of which suggest that different leadership styles are appropriate in different competitive situations. According to Turner and Muller⁸⁷ (2005), these leadership styles have been extracted from general management texts based on leadership considerations in organizations, and have created distinct effects.

Table 4. Modern Leadership Schools (Larson and et al, 2015)

School	Time	Core Topics	Prominent Researchers
Behavioral	1960-1940	Leaders can learn leadership. Leaders can be reconciled by specific behaviors.	Tanenbum & Schmit 1958
Contengency	1980-1960	Effective leadership depends on the position.	Fiedler 1979, Hersey & Blanchard 1969
Vision	2000-1980	Functional and Transformational leadership	Boss 1985, Kigen & Dan Haturg 2004
Emotional Intelligence	2000	Emotional Intelligence	Salvoy & Mayer1990, Golman and et al 2002
Aptness	2000	Key competence could be natural or they could be learned.	Dulviz & Hagues 2005

However, the four leadership styles described by House⁸⁸ (1971) are somewhat lacking distinctiveness⁸⁹. But a similar collection of leadership styles was created by Adizes (1976): Manufacturer, Manager, Entrepreneur, or Developer, and Integrator (PAEI). The apparent similarities between the four leadership styles by Desire (1971) have been identified in contingency and PAEI leadership styles. Nevertheless, the PAEI model clearly shows the differences between these styles, besides being an entrepreneur who is innovative and focuses on long-term successes, in primary typology Contingency schools are not included. This is more consistent with the classification created by Adizes (1979), because it has leaders who are often tired and do not function well in the situations controlled by the laws, bureaucratic producers, with Hard and non-flexible hard drive systems

In a research entitled "The Impact of Leadership on Organizational Performance", Hurduzeu⁹⁰ (2015) focuses on transformational leadership and its role in facilitating an increase in organizational performance. The results of this study indicate that: Understanding the relationship between transformational leaders and organizational performance is an important factor in increasing organizational effectiveness. However, the nature of this relationship and why and how leadership affects organizational performance has not yet been thoroughly analyzed.

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4. Summary and Conclusion

In this article, new leadership styles were introduced and new and modern theories in this field were mentioned. Leadership is one of the key points of organizational productivity and development.

5. References

- i. Adizes, I. K. (2004). *Management/Mismanagement Styles: How to Identity a Style and What to Do About It*, Library of Congress Cataloging-in-Publication Data.
- ii. Adizes, Ichack. (1988), "Dialectic convergence for Management of conflict", Los Angeles, MDOR institute, 1988.
- iii. Afacan, Mine. Yozgat, Uğur (2012), a qualitative analysis of charismatic leadership in creative teams: the case of Turkish TV series directors, *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 41, p 228.
- iv. Albert, G.A. (2003). *An Examination of Bass, Full range Leadership Model in Jamaican organization*. Dissertation for the degree of doctora, Nova Southeastern University.
- v. Andonovic, B., Spasovska, M. T., Dimitrov, A. (2014). *Integral Model for Distributing Functional Roles Within a Working Team*, *Quality of Life*, Vol (5): 5-18.
- vi. Avolio, B.J., & Gardner, W.L. 2005. *Authentic leadership development: Getting to the root of positive forms of leadership*. *Leadership Quarterly*, 16: 315-338.
- vii. Barret, G. V. and Depinet, R. L. (1991). *A Reconsideration of Testing Competence rather than Intelligence*, *Human Resource Management Review*, 1 (2): 97-105.
- viii. Bartram, D., Robertson, I. T., and Callinan, M. (2002). *Introduction: A Framework for Examining Organizational Effectiveness*, In I. T. Robertson, M. Callinan and D. Bartram (Eds), *Organizational Effectiveness: The Role of Psychology* (pp1-10), Chichester, UK: Wiley.
- ix. Bommer, W., Rubin, R. & Baldwin, T. (2004). *Setthng the stage for Effective Leadership Antecedents of transformational Leadership behavior*. *The Leadership Quarterly*, 15, 195-210.
- x. Brannick, M. T., Levine, E. L., and Morgeson, F. P. (2007). *Job and Work Analysis: Methods, Research and Application for Human Resource Management*, Sage Publication.
- xi. Bruce, A., Tucker, R., Russel, F., (2004), *Transformational and Transactional Leadership: Association with Attitudes toward Evidence Practice Leadership p: Association Whit Attitude Toward Evidence-Based Practice*, *Journal of leadership & Organizational Studies*. Flint: Spring, 10:103-112.
- xii. Carter, S. M., and Greer, C. R. (2013). *Strategic Leadership: Values, Styles, and Organizational Performance*, *Journal of Leadership and Organizational Studies*, 20 (4), 375-93.
- xiii. Dionne, Shelley D., Chun, Jae UK, Chanyu, Hao, Serban, Andra, Yammarino, Francis J., Spangler, William D (2012), *Article quality and publication impact via levels of analysis incorporation: An illustration with transformational/charismatic leadership*, *The Leadership Quarterly*, 23, p1014.
- xiv. Duckett, H, and Macfarlane, E. (2003), *Emotional Intelligence and Transformational Leadership in Retailing*, *Leadership & Organization Development Journal*, Vol. 24, 309-317.
- xv. Dweck, C. S. (1999). *Self-theories: Their role in motivation, personality and development*. Philadelphia: Psychology Press.
- xvi. Eiriz, V., Faria, A., and Barbosa, N. (2013). *Firm Growth and Innovation: Towards a Typology Strategy*, *Innovation: Management, Policy and Practice*. Vol 15, 97-111.
- xvii. Fry Louis, W. F. Locum, I. R & John, W. (2008). "Maximizing the Triple Bottem Line through Spiritual Leadership". *Organizational dynamics*, Vol, 37, PP: 86-96.
- xviii. García-Morales, V.J., Jiménez-Barrionuevo, M.M., Gutiérrez-Gutiérrez, L., (2012). "Transformational leadership influence on organizational performance through organizational learning and innovation", *Journal of Business Research* 65, p.p.1040–1050
- xix. Gao, Q. and Banerji, S. (2015). *The Growth Appraisal System for Chinese SMEs*, *Journal of Chinese Economic and Business Studies*, Vol. 13, No. 2, 175-193.
- xx. Green, P. C. (1999). *Building Robust Competencies: Linking Human Resource System to Organizational Strategies*, San Francisco: Jossey-Bass.
- xxi. Groysberg, B., McLean, A. N., and Nohria, N. (2006). *Are leaders' portable?* *Harvard Business Review*, 84(5), 92–100.
- xxii. Hersey, p. & Blanchard, H. k. (1997). "Management of organizational behavior", Englewood Cliffs, Prentice Hall.
- xxiii. Hogan, R., & Kaiser, R. B. (2005). "What we know about leadership. *Review of General Psychology*", 9, 169–180.
- xxiv. Horsman, J. H. (2001), "Perspectives of servant leadership and spirit in organization", A Dissertation for the degree Doctor of Philosophy, Gonzaga University.
- xxv. Hoy, W. K. & Miskel, C. G. (2013). *Educational administration: Theory, research, and practice*, 9th edition. New York: McGraw-Hill.

- xxvi. Huang, Xu; Iun, Joyce; Liu, Aili; Gong, Yaping, (2010), "Does participative leadership enhance work performance by inducing empowerment or trust? The differential effects on managerial and non-managerial subordinates", *Journal of Organizational Behavior, J. Organiz. Behav.* 31, 122–143 (2010), published online 28 July 2009 in Wiley InterScience.
- xxvii. Humphreys, J. H., & Einstein, W. O. (2003). *Nothing New Under the Sun: Transformational Leadership from a Historical Perspective. Management Decision*, Vol. 41, No. 1, pp. 85-95.
- xxviii. Humphreys, J.H. (2005). *Contextual implications for transformational and servant leadership: A historical approach. Management Decision*, 43(10): 1410-1431.
- xxix. Hurduzeu, R.E., (2015). "The impact of leadership on organizational performance", *Faculty of International Business and Economics, The Bucharest University of Economic Studies, SEA - Practical Application of Science Volume III, Issue 1 (7) / 2015*.
- xxx. Jackson, S. E. and Shuler, R. S. (1990). *Human Resource Planning: Challenges for I/O Psychologist*, 45: 223-239.
- xxxi. Jefferson, Anne L. (2010), "Performance Appraisal Applied to Leadership", *Educational Studies*, v36 n1 p111-114 Feb 2010.
- xxxii. Larsson, J., Eriksson, P. E., Olofsson, T., Simonsson, P. (2015). *Leadership in Civil Engineering: Effects of Project Managers Leadership Styles on Project Performance, Journal of Managing Engineering*, Vol 31: 1-11.
- xxxiii. Leban, W., & Zulauf, C. (2004). "Linking emotional intelligence abilities and transformational leadership styles". *Leadership & Organization Development Journal*, 25(7), 554-564.
- xxxiv. Lievens, F., Sanchez, J. I., and De Corte, W. (2004). *Easing the Inferential Leap in Competency Modeling: The Effects of Task Related Information and Subject Matter Expertise, Personnel Psychology*, 57: 881-904.
- xxxv. Levinson, H. (1989). *Designing and Managing Your Career*, Published by Harvard Business Press.
- xxxvi. Mandell, B. & Pherwani, S. (2003). *Relationship between Emotional Intelligence and Transformational Leadership Style: A Gender Comparison, Journal of Business and Psychology*, 17(3), 387-404.
- xxxvii. Nicolina, A. (2003). *Faculty and chair perspectives on leadership and its impacts on Departmental outcomes (Master's thesis)*. Arts McGill University, Montreal, Canada.
- xxxviii. Nusair, Naim., Ababneh, Raed., Bae, Yun Kyung. (2012). *The impact of transformational leadership style on innovation as perceived by public employees in Jordan, International Journal of Commerce and Management*, Vol. 22, No. 3, 182-201.
- xxxix. Ojokuku R. M, Odetayo T. A and Sajuyigbe A. S. (2012), "Impact of Leadership Style on Organizational Performance: A Case Study of Nigerian Banks", *American Journal of Business and Management Vol. 1, No. 4, 2012*, 202-207.
- xl. Omoh O. *Analysis of Servant Leadership Characteristics: A Case Study of Community College President, A Dissertation Presented in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirement for the Degree Doctor of Philosophy, Capella University. 2007. p 15*.
- xli. Pearlman, K. (1997). *Competencies: Issues in their Application, In R. C. Page, Competency Models: What Are they and Do They Work? Practitioner Forum Presented at Twelfth Annual Conference of the Society for Industrial and Organizational Psychology, St. Louis, MO*.
- xlii. Poor, J., Karoliny, Z., Dobrai, K., Slavic, A., Kerekes, K., Farkas, F., Allen, D., and Engle, S. (2014). *Factors Influencing Human Resource Management Solutions at Subsidiaries of Multinational Companies in Central and Eastern Europe, Journal of East-West Business*, 20: 93-119.
- xliii. Sanlam, C, O'Higgins, E. (2012), *Enhancing employee outcomes, Leadership & Organization Development Journal*, Vol. 33, No. 2, 149-174. Sanchez, J. I., and Levine, E. L. (2009). *What is (Or Should Be) The Difference Between Competency Sources of Variance Underlying Competency Ratings Modeling and Traditional Job Analysis? Human Resource Management Review*, 19: 53-63.
- xliv. Shippmann, J. S., Ash, R. A., Battista, M., Carr, L., Eyde, L. D., Hesketh, B., Kehoe, J., Pearlman, K., Prien, E. P. and Sanchez, J. I. (2000). *The Practice of Competency Modeling, Personnel Psychology*, 53: 703-740.
- xlv. Ulrich, D., Brockbank, W., Yeung, A. K., and Lake, D. G. (1995). *Human Resource Competencies: An Empirical Assessment, /human Resource Management*, 34: 473-495.
- xlvi. Vanderwerf, A. C. (2007), *Women and Transformational Leadership Undergraduate Honors in the Major Theses, Florida State University (Arts & Sciences – communication)*.
- xlvii. Van Vugt, M., Hogan, R., & Kaiser, R. B. (2008). "Leadership, followership, and evolution: Some lessons from the past". *American Psychologist*, 63, 182–196.

- xlvi. Vermeeren, B., Kuipers, B., and Steijn, B. (2014). *Does Leadership Style Make a Difference? Linking HRM, Job Satisfaction, and Organizational Performance*, *Review of Public Personnel Administration*, Vol. 34 (2), 174-95.
- xlix. Washington, R & Field, H. S. (2006), *Individual Difference in Servant Leadership: The Roles of Values and Personality*, *Leadership and Organization Development Journal*, 27(8), 700-71.
- l. Webb, K. (2003). *Presidents' Leadership Behaviors Associate with followers, Job Satisfaction Motivation toward Extra Effort and Presidential Effectiveness at Evangelical Colleges and Universities*. University of North Texas Ph. D Dissertations, Available at: www.proquest.com.
- li. Vermeeren, B., Kuipers, B., and Steijn, B. (2014). *Does Leadership Style Make a Difference? Linking HRM, Job Satisfaction, and Organizational Performance*, *Review of Public Personnel Administration*, Vol. 34 (2), 174-95.
- lii. Zaleznik, A. (1977) *Managers and leaders: Are they different?* *Harvard Business Review*, May-June, pp. 67-78. Reproduced in Jeffrey Sonnenfeld (1995) *Concepts of Leadership*, Co. Ltd.